

ISSUES OF RECOGNITION OF E-CMR AS A LEGALLY SIGNIFICANT DOCUMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

The article discusses the issues of recognizing the electronic consignment note (e-CMR) as a legally significant document in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The paper analyzes the theoretical foundations and legal framework governing the use of e-CMR, including the ratification of the Additional Protocol to the Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road (CMR). Practical issues, such as the legal recognition of e-CMR and challenges related to the integration of data into international transport and customs systems, are also addressed. The article provides recommendations for improving legislation, enhancing cross-border transport efficiency, and developing international cooperation. The challenges and prospects of implementing e-CMR in Uzbekistan are examined in the context of the digitalization of transport and logistics processes, which is an essential step towards enhancing the country's competitiveness and transit potential.

Keywords: e-CMR, electronic consignment note, legal recognition, international transport, CMR Convention, transport logistics, digitalization, data integration, Uzbekistan, international cooperation, electronic documents, legal regulation.

Digitization has a significant impact on modern logistics, transforming traditional approaches to organizing transport and forwarding activities. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of information technology in logistics and service provision is expanding the opportunities for clients to choose suppliers, logistics services, and optimal interaction schemes [1]. One of the key factors for the implementation of digital solutions in logistics is the self-organizing technologies that ensure the automation of processes and adaptation of logistics systems to changing conditions.

To legally support the use of electronic consignment notes, the Additional Protocol to the Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road (CMR) was adopted in 2008, regulating electronic consignment notes (eCMR). This Protocol is supplementary and creates a legal foundation for converting consignment notes into digital format without altering the main provisions of the CMR Convention. As of February 2025, the eCMR Protocol has 38 Contracting Parties. It should be emphasized that only countries that are Contracting Parties to the CMR Convention can become participants in the Protocol.

As is known, the Republic of Uzbekistan joined the Convention on the International Carriage of Goods by Road (hereinafter CMR) on May 19, 1956 [2]. On January 14, 2021, the Additional Protocol to the Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road, regulating electronic consignment notes (e-CMR), came into force in Uzbekistan, with Uzbekistan joining the Protocol based on Presidential Resolution No. PP-4842 of September 25, 2020 [3].

The Protocol provides for the implementation of the electronic consignment note, granting it legal force equivalent to that of a paper document, which facilitates the simplification and acceleration of international transportation contract processing via electronic communication means. Participation in the Protocol does not exclude the use of traditional paper forms, ensuring a flexible and gradual transition to digital format.

The introduction of e-CMR promotes the effective integration of various modes of transport within multimodal transport operations, expands the possibilities for managing operations regulated by the CMR Convention, and significantly reduces carrier and shipper costs related to the printing, processing, and storage of consignment notes and related documents.

Uzbekistan's accession to the Additional Protocol creates the prerequisites for simplifying transport and transit procedures, accelerating information exchange in logistics chains, and reducing administrative and time costs for national carriers.

The process of implementing electronic consignment notes (e-CMR) has been slow in practice, due to several practical factors. The main limiting factor is the lack of unified conceptual and technical specifications to guide participants in the transport process. Over the past seven years, several pilot projects have been conducted to test e-CMR, where various models of interaction have been trialed: between commercial structures, between government agencies, and in a "business-government" format.

The Republic of Uzbekistan actively participates in international road transport and attaches particular importance to the digitization of transport and logistics processes. In this regard, Uzbekistan is initiating the expansion of the use of electronic permits and encourages foreign countries to join the E-permit system and gradually implement the electronic consignment note (e-CMR). This measure will improve the efficiency of cross-border transport, simplify administrative procedures, and reduce costs for foreign trade participants.

An analysis of Uzbekistan's position on the digitalization of international transport demonstrates the government's commitment to actively integrating into global logistics and trade transport chains by implementing internationally recognized digital tools, such as the electronic consignment note (e-CMR). In the context of developing the Middle Corridor (Trans-Caspian International Transport Route — TITR), connecting Asia and Europe through Central Asia, the Caucasus, and Turkey, Uzbekistan is consistently advancing the digital transformation of logistics processes, seeing it as a key condition for enhancing the country's competitiveness and transit potential.

One of the central aspects of this policy is the implementation of e-CMR — the electronic equivalent of the traditional consignment note provided for by the Additional Protocol to the CMR Convention. This document, ensuring legal equivalence between the paper and electronic forms of the consignment note, opens the possibility for a full transition to digital document flow, reducing transactional costs, speeding up border procedures, and shortening delivery times. This is especially important for multimodal and

cross-border transport, where fast, transparent, and coordinated interaction between different participants in the transport chain is required.

As part of interstate cooperation, Uzbekistan is actively participating in testing and gradually implementing the e-CMR system and electronic permits (E-permit) together with Turkey and Azerbaijan. These digital tools are already being tested in pilot projects aimed at improving cross-border transport efficiency, including within the Baku–Tbilisi–Kars route and using the Baku International Sea Trade Port. Support for these initiatives at the political level, including bilateral and multilateral agreements within the frameworks of the SCO, ECO, and other regional formats, highlights Uzbekistan's systemic approach in this area.

It should be noted that the implementation of e-CMR requires not only technical adaptation of logistics infrastructure but also the alignment of national legislation with international electronic document standards, including issues of authentication, legal force of electronic documents, data protection, and interagency interaction. In this context, Uzbekistan will need to address a range of tasks to improve the regulatory framework, form a digital transportation ecosystem, and train personnel to work in the field of digital logistics.

The fundamental difference between the CMR Convention and the e-CMR Protocol lies in the approach to processing transport documentation. While the CMR Convention insists on the presence of a paper document with mandatory and, when necessary, additional details, the e-CMR Protocol, in accordance with Article 5, requires an agreement between the parties not only on the digital format of the consignment note but also on the procedures for its use and adherence to those procedures. Special attention is given to issues of authenticity and reliability (Article 3).

Moreover, according to paragraph 1 of Article 2 of the Protocol, during its implementation, it is allowed to issue in electronic form not only the consignment note itself but also any other messages, statements, instructions, requests, and reservations

related to the performance of the carriage contract regulated by the CMR Convention. Thus, the e-CMR Protocol extends its legal impact to the entire range of procedures provided by the Convention, expanding the application of digital technologies in international road transport.

Today, a number of key advantages of using e-CMR can already be identified [5]:

Cost reduction due to accelerated document flow, reduced manual data entry, and no need to handle paper documents, send faxes, scan, email, or maintain paper archives. Furthermore, the electronic consignment note facilitates faster invoicing and reduces discrepancies during delivery and receipt of goods. According to a study conducted for the Danish Ministry of Transport, processing one paper consignment note takes about 23 minutes, whereas an electronic consignment note is processed in 9 minutes, leading to a 14-minute reduction in processing time. Companies testing e-CMR reported a 70% reduction in administrative costs and a 59% reduction in transport document processing time [6]. Transporeon notes that transitioning to e-CMR can save up to €13 per consignment note, accelerate document processing, and increase operation transparency [7].

Increased transparency: ensuring data accuracy, the ability to track and monitor cargo, and access to real-time information, including confirmation of loading and delivery events. Thanks to its digital form, e-CMR easily integrates with other services used by transport companies — such as customs declaration systems, transport management systems, and fleet management systems. Digitizing the consignment note eliminates, and often completely eradicates, many inefficiencies. Replacing paper with a digital format reduces data processing errors, prevents inconsistencies, and ensures real-time access to data throughout the process, significantly improving transparency [8].

However, for the successful implementation of the e-CMR system, several existing obstacles still need to be overcome. This requires active and targeted actions from both government agencies and businesses. It is important not only to promote digital literacy

and reduce resistance to innovation among participants but also to create all the necessary conditions for a rapid and efficient transition to electronic consignment notes at the national level [9].

The main issue for Uzbekistan remains the integration of its system with transport systems and customs services of foreign countries, which may require significant efforts to develop interaction standards and ensure data compatibility [10].

Currently, Uzbekistan lacks full integration of national electronic consignment notes with the e-CMR system for international transport. Nevertheless, the country is actively progressing in the digitalization of transport processes, opening up prospects for future integration with international standards [11].

As noted by Raluca Marian, Director of the IRU delegation to the European Union: "One of the key problems limiting the implementation of e-CMR is the lack of compatibility between different participants in the process. It should be noted that the technologies used by various providers do not always ensure proper communication between different systems."

The process of integrating e-CMR will require modernization of existing national systems, including the development and implementation of digital signature systems, as well as establishing interaction with the customs services of other countries. An important aspect is also ensuring compliance with international standards for data security and legal significance, which will ensure the reliability and legality of using the electronic consignment note at the international level.

The transition to the e-CMR system in Uzbekistan is likely to take place in the coming years, contributing to the integration of existing national electronic consignment notes into international practice. This will simplify international transport procedures and improve logistics operations in the context of cross-border trade.

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